

DIGITAL SOLUTIONS AND ECO-FRIENDLY PRACTICES AS DRIVERS OF BUSINESS COMPETITIVENESS AMONG MSMES IN CAGAYAN DE ORO, PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the relationship between digital solutions and eco-friendly practices and their influence on business competitiveness. Using the Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory and Michael Porter's Competitive Advantage Theory, the researcher evaluates how the adoption of digital marketing solutions and eco-friendly practices enhances key areas such as market positioning, financial performance, and operational efficiency, thereby strengthening overall competitiveness. Data were collected from MSME owners and representatives in Cagayan de Oro City through surveys and interviews and were analyzed using statistical methods. Additionally, factor analysis was applied to the survey instrument to ensure the validity and reliability of the constructs measured. Findings indicate that strong digital adoption in sales and marketing, combined with eco-friendly practices, enhances business competitiveness, particularly in market positioning, financial performance, and operational efficiency. Results of the adjusted R-squared value of 96% indicates that the model explains a substantial proportion of the variation in business competitiveness. The qualitative findings highlight two key themes sustaining MSME competitiveness: adaptive and ethical strategies for sustainability and customer-centric innovation and digital transformation. These findings affirm that MSMEs that actively integrate digital innovation and environmental responsibility are better positioned for sustainable growth and long-term relevance. In light of these findings, Future research could incorporate participant feedback and expand the analysis to explore innovative, evidence-based approaches linking digital transformation and sustainability to MSME competitiveness and growth. Collaborations with government agencies, industry

stakeholders, and MSME organizations may also provide comprehensive insights to address emerging challenges and support the economic development of Cagayan de Oro City.

Keywords: *digital solutions, eco-friendly practices, business competitiveness*

INTRODUCTION

Micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) are widely recognized as key drivers of employment, innovation, and economic growth. International studies have shown that MSMEs face increasing pressure to remain competitive amid rapid digitalization and rising sustainability expectations (Plečko & Bradač Hojnik, 2024). While global literature has examined digital transformation and *eco-friendly practices* separately, limited studies have explored their combined influence on *business competitiveness*, particularly in developing economies where resource constraints shape adoption decisions.

At the national level, the Philippine government has emphasized digital transformation as a strategic priority for MSMEs, highlighting its potential to improve market reach, operational efficiency, and resilience (DTI, 2023; PwC Philippines, 2020). Concurrently, national market studies indicate a growing preference among Filipino consumers for environmentally responsible products and practices, especially eco-friendly packaging, reflecting heightened environmental awareness (Dena, et al., 2023). However, most Philippine-based studies focus either on digital adoption challenges or sustainability awareness in isolation, with limited empirical evidence linking these practices to perceived *business competitiveness* among MSMEs.

In the local context of Cagayan de Oro City, MSMEs continue to encounter difficulties in understanding how digital tools and *eco-friendly practices* can be strategically leveraged to gain a competitive advantage. Many enterprises remain uncertain about which *digital solutions* enhance performance and how sustainability initiatives translate into tangible business outcomes (Triviño, 2023). There is a notable lack of localized, data-driven studies examining how MSMEs in emerging urban economies simultaneously respond to technological change and environmental demands.

Addressing these gaps, the present study examines the influence of two independent variables—*digital solutions* and *eco-friendly practices*—on *business competitiveness* among MSMEs in Cagayan de Oro City. *Digital solutions* include digital marketing strategies and automation tools (Santos et al., 2022; Deskera, 2025; Gupta, 2025), while *eco-friendly practices* focus on resource efficiency, waste reduction, and environmentally responsible operations. Business competitiveness is assessed in terms of perceived market position, operational efficiency, and overall performance.

By integrating international perspectives, national policy priorities, and local business realities, this study contributes to Sustainable Development Goal 13 (Climate Action) and provides empirical evidence to support context-sensitive strategies for MSMEs. The findings

are expected to inform MSME owners, policymakers, and support institutions on how aligned digital and sustainability practices can strengthen competitiveness in a rapidly evolving business environment.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

This study assumes that *digital solutions* and *eco-friendly practices* have a positive influence on the *business competitiveness* of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Cagayan de Oro City. This study aims to explore whether MSMEs' adoption of these strategies can improve market efficiency and operational processes, thereby enhancing their competitive advantage. The study is grounded in relevant business theories that provide insights into the influence of *digital solutions* and environmentally sustainable practices on MSME competitiveness.

According to the Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory, the company's competitive advantage comes from its valuable, rare, and unique resources and capabilities. Drawing on the RBV, MSMEs that leverage *digital solutions* (e.g., e-commerce and digital marketing tools) and sustainable business practices (e.g., eco-friendly production methods, energy efficiency, and waste management) can enhance operational efficiency and market presence (Bindeeba et al., 2025). These digital and eco-friendly capabilities are viewed as strategic resources that enable MSMEs to outperform their competitors, particularly when they are difficult for others to replicate. The RBV provides a basis for understanding how these tools and practices can serve as competitive resources for MSMEs in Cagayan de Oro.

In addition, Michael Porter's Competitive Advantage Theory states that firms may achieve superior performance by providing unique products or services (differentiation) or by offering the same or similar products or services at a lower cost (cost leadership). MSMEs can compete on differentiation through *digital solutions* that enhance customer engagement, personalized/targeted marketing, and optimized service offerings (Sunggara et al., 2024). Similarly, responsible practices enable MSMEs to target eco-sensitive consumers, develop brand loyalty, and establish a competitive niche (SME Scale, 2024). Porter's theory suggests that adopting digital and sustainable practices can give a competitive edge through differentiation or operational efficiency.

The conceptual framework illustrates the relationship between *digital solutions* and *eco-friendly practices*, independent variables that influence *business competitiveness*, and the dependent variable. This relationship is channeled through key areas like market positioning, financial performance, and operational efficiency. The framework emphasizes that while digital and green practices may offer direct advantages, their actual value often emerges through the improvements they bring to how a business operates, competes, and adapts as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of the Study
The schematic figure illustrates the relationship between the Independent and Dependent Variables of the Study.

Research Questions

This study examined the impact of *digital solutions* and *eco-friendly practices* on the *business competitiveness* of MSMEs in Cagayan de Oro, focusing on market positioning, financial performance, and operational efficiency. The specific questions this research aimed to address include:

1. What is the MSMEs' extent of the use of *digital solutions* for sales and marketing?
2. What is the MSMEs' use of *eco-friendly practices*?
3. What is the level of the MSMEs' *business competitiveness* considering:
 - a. market positioning
 - b. financial performance; and
 - c. Operational efficiency?
4. Do the MSMEs' use of *digital solutions* and *eco-friendly practices* significantly influence their *business competitiveness*?
5. What are the participants' experiences in relation to their *business competitiveness*?

METHODOLOGY

This paper provides the methodology for conducting the study. It contains details about the research design, participants, sampling plan, instruments, scoring system, validity and reliability of the instruments, data collection and ethical considerations, and statistical analysis of the data.

Research Design

This study employed an explanatory sequential mixed-method design, consisting of two phases: an initial quantitative phase followed by a qualitative phase to further explain the results. This approach allows numerical data to identify patterns and relationships, which are then clarified and enriched through interviews and other qualitative insights. By integrating both methods, the study provides a more comprehensive and well-contextualized understanding of the research problem, leading to stronger and more robust conclusions.

Participants and Sampling Procedure

From the Cagayan de Oro Trade and Investment Promotions Center (Oro-TIPC) official website publication, the City Finance Department records show that Cagayan de Oro recorded a total of 27,598 businesses registered as of 2019 and around 29,500 as of 2022 (published on November 23, 2023,). Of these, 99.35% fall under micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs). The Participants in the study included business owners or representatives from the MSMEs in Cagayan de Oro City that the researcher has selected. They were qualified for the study if they have managed the business. The study adopted the work of Dr. Ralph Jay Magsalay entitled *"Quantifying Central Limit Theorem Convergence: A Monte Carlo Simulation Approach to Minimum Sample Size."* Dr. Magsalay's research emphasized that, for many statistical estimations, a sample size of approximately 200 is sufficient to achieve a reliable approximation of population parameters in accordance with the Central Limit Theorem. This recommended that reducing the sample size to 200 still allowed the study to maintain statistical validity and draw meaningful insights from the data collected.

The study utilized a systematic random sampling with replacement for non-response technique. A complete population count of the sampling unit that the researchers required was obtained. The researchers collected the sample using systematic sampling from the list. In case the selected participant was not responsive or unavailable, then another participant from the population was selected randomly as a member. Ensured that the desirable sample size was achieved while maintaining the statistical validity and representativeness of the study. Individuals participating in the study were aged at least 23 years old or over and had relevant experience, or involvement, managing the business.

For the qualitative part of the study, 5 participants were selected. All the participants were willing to give consent and took part in the interview. Moreover, participants must be available during the duration of the data collection for the qualitative task and also capable of effective communication either in vernacular or English. Individuals were excluded from the study who could not give consent or participate effectively due to mental or communication disabilities. Moreover, those presently participating in possibly biasing studies or programs that are in conflict were disqualified. Anyone who had no relevant exposure or experience related to the study topic was excluded. Moreover, the research excluded participants who could not commit to the planned qualitative interviews. Also excluded were participants whose medical or psychological conditions could pose a disruption in their participation and/or a compromise in data reliability.

The site selected for the qualitative interviews proved to be very appropriate as it is easily accessible and directly useful to the study population. It provided a calm and confidential setting that was conducive to open and honest deliberations which was key in gathering rich qualitative data. The site's accessibility contributed to the participants' feelings of comfort and willingness to engage fully during the interviews. Moreover, the site has the right on-site support, such as sufficient space, seating facilities, and minimal distractions, to data collection.

Research Instrument

To successfully and efficiently gather the necessary data, the researcher used a combination of modified questionnaire. The questionnaire was arranged into six sections, each related to one of the study's variables: *digital solutions* for sales and marketing, *eco-friendly practices*, *business competitiveness* in terms of market positioning, financial performance and operational efficiency. For part 1, *digital solutions* for sales and marketing, it was based on the instrument created by Raymund Habaradas et. Al (2024). For part 2, *eco-friendly practices* were from the study of Chong et al (2024). For part 3, *business competitiveness* in terms of market positioning was based from the study of Chenglin Qing and Shanyue Jin (2023). For part 4, *business competitiveness* in terms of financial performance was drawn from the study of John Pagaddut (2021) and part 5, *business competitiveness* in terms of operational efficiency was from the study of Bambang Triwahyono, et al. (2023).

The researcher collected detailed and well-organized data for the study. The survey used a five-point Likert scale to measure opinions and attitudes, where subjects were instructed to select the best response for each item (1 = strongly disagree, 2 =disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree, 5 =strongly agree).

This study utilized a structured questionnaire as the main research instrument to collect data on the influence of digital solutions and *eco-friendly practices* on business competitiveness among MSMEs in Cagayan de Oro.

Validity and Reliability of the Research Instruments

The final version of the survey was prepared from the comments made by the panel of experts and subject-matter specialists verified the research instruments. Following these adjustments, a pilot test was run utilizing thirty subjects. Afterward, it was found that the internal consistency and reliability of the instrument could be measured by Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient. Following Hair et al. (2019) and Fornell and Larcker (1981) recommendations, factor analysis is conducted. To ensure the validity and reliability of the measuring instruments that were used, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and Composite Reliability were involved in the process.

The reliability analysis conducted through the coefficients gathered showed all constructs possess strong internal consistency. All values exceeded the recommended reliability

benchmark of 0.70, demonstrating that the items consistently measured their expected constructs. The measures have reliable accuracy as the *Digital Solutions* with value .939, *Eco-Friendly Practices* with value .930, and their further *Business Competitiveness* component Market Positioning with value .970, Operational Efficiency with value .924, and Financial Performance with value .943 tests confirm this finding. Thus, the measures can enhance the reliability of the overall research instrument.

Scoring Procedure

The key variables were measured using a 5-point Likert scale in the questionnaire to assess participant's attitude and views. The questionnaire had five-point scale for participants to rate their degree of agreement to the statements with options ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree. This scoring method is commonly used in social science research because it is simple, reliable, and can capture varying degrees of agreement or disagreement (Likert, 1932; DeVellis, 2016). The explanation below describes the questionnaire used to measure participants' understanding using a 5-Likert scale that scores a one to five.

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
5	4.51 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
4	3.51 – 4.50	Agree	High
3	2.51 – 3.50	Moderate	neutral
2	1.51 – 2.50	Disagree	Low
1	1.00 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Data Gathering Procedure and Ethical Considerations

Upon review by Lourdes College Research Ethics Committee (LC REC), the researcher obtained ethical clearance for the said study. A questionnaire designed from a Five-Point Likert scale was used to collect data. Respondents voiced their opinions on a scaled basis, from strong disagreement to strong manifestation. Depending on participant availability, data collection was either administered through paper-and-pencil questionnaires which were given and collected in person for proper guidance and clarification of participant queries, or else through electronic questionnaires for privacy and convenience.

This data collection method is in line with the ethical principles as stipulated in the Belmont report. These principles include respect for persons, beneficence and justice. Respect for Persons is made sure by providing clear instructions and opportunities for questions; Beneficence is maintained by protecting participant confidentiality through secure storage and encryption; and Justice is showed in selecting methods that accommodate all participants reasonably, including those with limited digital access.

The stored data for analysis were managed according to a guideline. The researcher informed the participants about the purpose, procedure, risk and benefits of the study.

The researcher took consent from the participants but specially mentioned that they can withdraw their consent anytime without any punishment. The safety of the participants was prioritized and it ensured their confidentiality. Moreover, there were no harms done during the study.

To ensure a diverse and representative sample of MSMEs, strict inclusion and exclusion criteria was utilized to see to it that vulnerable groups were not exploited. In accordance with the Belmont Principles, the study adhered to the highest ethical standards and received approvals by the relevant ethical boards and the data protection law.

Data collection was scheduled with business owners at breaks, after business hours or non-operating days to not affect the operations of the business. Advance information was given to make sure of it.

Trustworthiness

To ensure trustworthiness in qualitative research, it is necessary to demonstrate if the findings accurately reflect the point of view of the participants. The research of this study was undertaken with self-diligence based on the guidelines of Lincoln and Guba (1985). These criteria (credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability) together strengthen the integrity and quality of the study in question. Based on these criteria, the researcher investigated the MSME participants' experiences related to *business competitiveness*, specifically concerning *digital solutions* and sustainable practices.

In the initial criterion which deals with credibility, the researcher ascertained the accuracy of the participants' stories through the discussion afterward. A qualitative research expert was asked to comment on the coding procedures, interview transcripts, and emerging themes to verify that the interpretations were truly those of the respondents. At the time of interviews, participants were checked through re-statement of main response to check correctness of meaning.

Transferability refers to the degree to which the results may have meaning in other settings (Padgett, 2008). To bolster this claim, the researcher presented descriptions of the characteristics, business conditions of MSMEs, and the adoption of digital and environmentally friendly practices. Because of these specifics, the reader can assess whether similar findings would apply in MSMEs or similar business situations. The results were linked to previous studies on SME competitiveness, sustainability practices, and digital adoption.

In order to be dependable, the researcher set aside his assumptions throughout the data gathering and analysis process to minimize personal bias. An independent qualitative audit was used to assess the audit trail including raw data, coding outputs, analytic memos and thematic interpretations to check consistency in our approach. Incorporated the auditor's recommendations to enhance the clarity, consistency, and representativeness of the data.

Ultimately, confirmability was achieved through systematic documentation and reflexive practices. Project documentation included interviews logs coding materials analytic notes and project documents. These processes and the external audit ensure the conclusions are derived from the participants' perspective rather than the researcher's assumptions.

Reflexivity

This study required reflexivity to examine the researcher's beliefs, assumptions and positionality that may influence the interpretation of the experiences provided by the participants. The researcher was involved in the Department of Trade and Industry. She admitted to helping MSMEs and understands how this affects data collection and qualitative data analysis. The researcher recognized this position and put in a conscious effort to listen openly, hold back their expectations, and prioritize what participants shared. The reflexivity practice helped to enhance the transparency and integrity of the study providing support that the findings are based on the MSME owners' viewpoint themselves.

Statistical Treatment

To address the research problems, statistical tools and procedures were used.

Research questions 1-3 used descriptive analysis such as frequency, percentage, and mean distribution to describe the *business competitiveness*.

Moreover, data on research question 4 used regression analysis to examine if there is a significant influence of *digital solutions* and *eco-friendly practices* on *business competitiveness*. Lastly, data related to research question 5 were organized using thematic analysis by Braun and Clarke (2006) to determine the participants' view of *business competitiveness* regarding *digital solutions* and *eco-friendly practices*.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. What is the MSMES' extent of the use of *digital solutions* for sales and marketing?

Table 1 shows the extent of *digital solution* use for sales and marketing among MSMEs. The data illustrate the frequency with which participants use different digital platforms and tools to promote and sell their products or services.

The overall mean of 3.57 with a standard deviation of 1.01 indicates that, on average, MSMEs reveal a high extent of *digital solution* usage in their marketing and sales operations. Consistent with this finding, a significant portion of respondents rated their usage as high (23.39%) and very high (25.81%), showing the growing integration of online marketing strategies, e-commerce platforms, and digital advertising to expand market reach and improve competitiveness. This pattern is supported by the studies of OECD (2023) and Alalwan et al. (2022), which highlight that the adoption of digital marketing

tools significantly enhances business visibility, customer engagement, and operational efficiency.

Table 1
Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the MSMEs' Extent of the Use of Digital Solutions for Sales and Marketing

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	32	25.81
3.51-4.50	Agree	High	29	23.39
2.51-3.50	Neutral	Moderate	43	34.68
1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low	19	15.32
1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	1	0.81
Total			124	100.0
Overall Mean				3.57
Interpretation				High
SD				1.01

Research Question 2. What is the level of MSMEs' use of eco-friendly practices?

Table 2 presents the extent to which MSMEs utilized *eco-friendly practices* in their business operations. The overall mean of 3.94 with a standard deviation of 0.88 indicates a high level of adoption of environmentally sustainable practices among the participants. This result suggests that eco-friendly initiatives were commonly incorporated into daily operations. The frequency distribution further supports this finding, showing that a majority of participants rated their practices as high (33.06%) or very high (29.84%), which aligns with the computed mean. Overall, the results indicate that many MSMEs reported consistent engagement in environmentally responsible practices as part of their operational activities.

These findings imply that MSMEs are becoming more forward-thinking in implementing environmentally responsible strategies to meet sustainability demands. In line with this, Li et al. (2023) emphasized that MSMEs increasingly use entrepreneurial marketing behaviors to integrate sustainable, including environmental practices, into their operations to improve long-term practicality and benefits for stakeholders.

Table 2
Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the MSMEs' Level of Use of Eco-Friendly Practices.

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	37	29.84
3.51-4.50	Agree	High	41	33.06
2.51-3.50	Neutral	Moderate	41	33.06

1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low	5	4.03
1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	0	0.00
Total			124	100.0
Overall Mean				3.94
Interpretation				High
SD				0.88

Research Question 3. What is the level of the MSMEs' business competitiveness considering:

- 3.1 Market Positioning;**
- 3.2 Financial performance; and**
- 3.3 Operational Efficiency?**

Table 3 shows that MSMEs demonstrated a high level of *business competitiveness* across all three dimensions. Operational efficiency recorded the highest mean (3.85), followed by financial performance (3.82) and market positioning (3.66). The overall mean of 3.78 with a standard deviation of 0.83 indicates that, on average, participants perceived their businesses as highly competitive in terms of operations, finances, and market presence.

Table 3
Summary Table of Business Competitiveness

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Market Positioning	3.66	High	0.99
Financial Performance	3.82	High	0.86
Operational efficiency	3.85	High	0.90
Business Competitiveness	3.78	High	0.83

The overall high competitiveness of MSMEs observed in this study aligns with recent literature emphasizing the strategic integration of sustainability, financial management, and operational effectiveness. Empirical findings show that MSMEs that embed green innovation and sustainability into their operations achieve stronger financial and market outcomes (Setyaningrum et al., 2023; Sudirman et al., 2024). Innovation and responsible management, supported by technology alignment, further enhance performance and competitive advantage (Becerra-Vicario et al., 2023; Molete et al., 2025). Global analyses also confirm that sustainability and digital transformation strengthen SMEs' productivity and resilience (OECD, 2023; World Bank, 2022). Collectively, these studies validate that aligning environmental responsibility, financial prudence, and operational efficiency positions MSMEs for long-term competitiveness and growth.

Research Question 4. Do the MSMES' use of digital solutions and eco-friendly practices significantly influence their business competitiveness?

Ho1: MSMES' use of digital solutions and *eco-friendly practices* does not significantly influence their *business competitiveness*.

Ho2: MSMES' use of *digital solutions* does not significantly influence their *business competitiveness*.

Ho3: MSMES' use of *eco-friendly practices* does not significantly influence their *business competitiveness*.

Table 4 demonstrates the regression analysis on the use of digital solutions and *eco-friendly practices* by MSMEs as determinants of their *business competitiveness*. The model yielded a high coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.966$), indicating that the combined influence of *digital solutions* and *eco-friendly practices* explains 96.6% of the variance in *business competitiveness*. The overall model was statistically significant ($F = 1740.22$, $p < 0.01$), signifying a strong predictive relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Both determinants obtained p-values of .000, which are below the 0.01 significance level, leading to the rejection of the null hypotheses (H_3). This implies that the use of *digital solutions* and *eco-friendly practices* has a significant influence on the competitiveness of MSMEs.

The regression results further revealed that both *digital solutions* and *eco-friendly practices* are significant predictors of MSMEs' *business competitiveness*. Specifically, the use of *digital solutions* ($B = 0.424$, $\beta = 0.515$, $p < 0.01$) indicates that for every one-unit increase in the extent of digital solution utilization, there is an expected 0.424-unit increase in *business competitiveness*, holding other factors constant. This suggests that MSMEs investing more in digital tools, such as online marketing, e-commerce platforms, and customer data analytics, are more likely to enhance their visibility, operational efficiency, and customer engagement. According to Vial (2021), digital transformation enables small firms to optimize their processes and foster innovation, ultimately giving them a competitive edge.

Similarly, Zhang et al. (2022) emphasize that digital capability enables firms to respond swiftly to market changes, build stronger customer relationships, and increase profitability. Given the p-value below 0.01, the null hypothesis (Ho2), that *digital solutions* have no significant influence on MSMEs' competitiveness, is rejected. Hence, digital adoption directly empowers MSMEs to compete effectively in a dynamic marketplace.

Qualitative data from the participants further illustrate how digitalisation was perceived to support *business competitiveness*. Sheila (L50–53) shared, “Kung dili ka active sa online... ma behind gyud ka... daghan kompetensiya sa Shopee ug Facebook...” (“*If you are not active online, you will inevitably fall behind, especially with the high level of competition on platforms like Shopee and Facebook.*”), highlighting the need for MSMEs to maintain an active presence on digital platforms such as social media and online marketplaces to remain visible and competitive. Similarly, Mark (L20–23) noted, “More importantly, sa sustainability... kung gwapo kag produkto, mas gwapo ako. Ang pangutana ana, kinsa mo lahatay,” (“*More importantly, in terms of sustainability, even if you have a good product and I have an even better one, the real question is, who will*”).

endure in the long run?”), pointing to sustainability as a key consideration in long-term competitiveness. Together, these narratives suggest that participants viewed digitalization and sustainable practices as important factors in maintaining competitiveness over time, which is consistent with the quantitative findings of the study.

Table 4
Regression Analysis of the MSMEs’ Use of Digital Solutions and Eco-friendly Practices on their Business Competitiveness

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
(Constant)	.079	.065		1.209	.229
Digital Solutions	.424	.017	.515	24.97**	.000
Eco-friendly practices	.556	.020	.587	28.47**	.000

Model Summary

R = 0.983 R² = 0.966 Adj. R² = 0.966 F=1740.22** p = .000

**significant at 0.01 level

Meanwhile, *eco-friendly practices* (B = 0.556, β = 0.587, $p < 0.01$) exert an even more substantial influence on competitiveness. This means that for every one-unit increase in *eco-friendly practices*, there is an expected 0.556-unit increase in MSME competitiveness. This highlights that environmentally conscious strategies, such as sustainable packaging, energy efficiency, and waste reduction, have a positive influence on both reputation and operational sustainability. Studies by Fernando and Wah (2022) and Li et al. (2023) support this finding, asserting that sustainability-oriented enterprises attract eco-conscious consumers, gain regulatory advantages, and improve long-term profitability. In light of the statistical results, the null hypothesis (H0.3), which posits that *eco-friendly practices* do not significantly affect MSME competitiveness, is also rejected.

Qualitative data further illustrate this link between sustainability and competitiveness. As Mark (L112-114) emphasized, “Because we stick to our guns, environmental, people, planet, profit. Ikaduha si planet eh. Ikatulo pa gyud tos profit,” (“Because we adhere to our core principles: environment, people, planet, and profit. In fact, the planet comes second, and profit only comes third. “reflecting how prioritizing environmental responsibility over short-term gains builds trust and strengthens long-term business viability. Likewise, Mark (L191–193) added, “Nagshape sa amo, sa ako is kinahanglan naa ka sa imo vision. You can be competitive... but the vision stays the same. That is what makes you competitive enough.” (“*What shapes us, and in my case, it is essential to stay true to one’s vision. One can be competitive, but the vision must remain constant. This consistency is what ultimately makes one truly competitive.*”), highlighting that maintaining a consistent sustainability vision contributes to lasting market differentiation.

These insights complement the regression findings by showing that MSMEs grounded in eco-friendly values not only achieve operational efficiency but also cultivate a resilient brand identity that sustains competitiveness over time.

Research Question 5. What are the participants’ experiences in relation to their business competitiveness?

Table 5
Themes from categories and exemplars of the experiences of participants in relation to their business competitiveness.

Core Theme	Categories	Exemplars
1. Adaptive and Ethical Strategies for Sustainability	1. Adaptability, Resilience, and Sustainability	<p>“Ang pagkacompetitive sa Negosyo kai kanang kabalo ka moadjust ug molevel sa uban... magpabilin na lig-on ug kasaligan pud sa customer.” (<i>Business competitiveness involves the ability to adapt and align with industry standards while maintaining stability and reliability for customers.</i>)</p> <p>Sheila (Lines 11–13):</p>
		<p>“Pandemic. Ang ano lang gyud namo adtong pandemic gyud, wala lay mawad-an ug trabaho. Mao gyud, mao ra gyud. Even ana, na dli ka mokita. Dawata nana... So, ako nay nagawas-gawas, nagtuyok tuyok ako ra isa.” (<i>During the pandemic, our main concern was simply that no one would lose their jobs. Even then, income was minimal, and we had to accept the situation. As a result, I had to go out and work on my own, moving around independently to sustain the business.</i>)</p> <p>Mark (Lines 155-160)</p>
		<p>“The strategy is always have that positive outlook... Pasabot, mahuman raman gyud ni... gidawat namo nahitabo ni then we move forward.” (<i>The strategy is always to maintain a positive outlook. It means that the situation will eventually pass; we accept what has happened and then move forward.</i>)</p> <p>Mark (Lines 179–185)</p>
	2. Ethical and Strategic Business Practices	<p>“Kung dili ka kabalo aning tulo (pricing, location and target market) mura siya ug wala siya nakaplano na business, murage nana siya bah. Mura siya ug trial and error.” (<i>If you do not understand these three—pricing, location, and</i></p>

	<p><i>target market—it is as if your business has no proper plan; it becomes more like trial and error.”)</i> Claire (Lines 147-153)</p>
	<p>“Naa may mga butang na dili, non-negotiable man gyud para sa amo. So, sige na lang. Kung magansi me din ma gansi me.” (<i>“There are certain things that are truly non-negotiable for us. So we simply accept it. If we incur losses, then we incur losses.”</i>) Mark (Lines 105-106)</p>
	<p>“Naa tay wholesale naa puy retail. Bahalag gamay ang patong basta wholesale, daghan. Mao nang strategy.” (<i>“We offer both wholesale and retail. Even if the profit margin for wholesale is small, the volume is high. That is our strategy.”</i>) Rolly (Lines 81-82)</p>
<p>3. Financial management and stability</p>	<p>“Dli sagolan. Example, magorder ka sa Shopee, dapat dili nimo kuhaon sa Negosyo. Lahi sa personal. Lahi sa business. Even kami magkuha me diria, bayaran namo kai mao nang isa sa maka failure satong Negosyo and utang.” (<i>“We do not mix finances. For example, if you order something from Shopee, you should not take money from the business. Personal funds are separate from business funds. Even when we get items from our own store, we pay for them because mixing finances—and accumulating debt—is one of the things that can lead to business failure.”</i>) Jade (Lines 60-63)</p>
	<p>“Nalipay ta nga medyo modako dako ang atong daily sales. Halin. Murag diha na, malipay ta na modako dako pud ang atong income.” (<i>“We are pleased that our daily sales have started to increase. When sales grow, we become even more motivated because it also means our income is improving.”</i>) Rolly (Lines 54-55)</p>
	<p>“Ang Negosyo sa uban na prinsipyo nanginahanglan jud ni ug buffer. Kung wala ang buffer, murag paengon jud ta ana ug down.” (<i>“A business, based on the principles we follow, really needs a financial buffer. Without that buffer, the business is at risk of going down.”</i>) Rolly (Lines 20-22)</p>

	4. Values, Vision, and Authentic Brand Identity	<p>“Pangitag paagi, without losing your identity.” (<i>core brand authenticity</i>) (“<i>Find ways to innovate, but without losing your identity.</i>”) Mark (Lines 48-49)</p>
		<p>“Active in your own sense. Pasabot, active ka, at par ka sa uban, pero dili ni mo walaon ang imong identity.” (<i>maintaining brand essence</i>) (“<i>Be active in your own way. This means being engaged and keeping pace with others, but without compromising your identity.</i>”) Mark (Lines 39-41)</p>
2. Customer-Centric Innovation and Digital Transformation	1. Customer-Centered Excellence	<p>“Atimanon natog maayo atong customer para ang customer man gud is kung mayo ka moentertain sa ilaha magbalik balik gyud na sa imo, dili jud ka mabyaan.” (<i>We take good care of our customers because if you provide excellent service, they will keep coming back, ensuring customer loyalty.</i>) Jade (Lines 17-19)</p> <p>“Build up imong social media... customer service... experience sa product...” (<i>Focus on building up your social media presence, enhancing customer service, and improving the overall product experience.</i>) Claire (Lines 99-103)</p> <p>“Presyo... pagapproach sa customer... porma sa atong nawong... bahalag walay makeup pahiyom lang...” (<i>Pricing, how you approach the customer, and your appearance—all matter; even without makeup, a simple smile goes a long way.</i>) Rolly (Lines 69-75)</p>
	2. Digitalization and Online Presence	<p>“Kabalo pud me moadopt sa bag ong mga teknolohiya... gagamit me ug more on sa online.” (<i>We are also capable of adopting new technologies, with a strong focus on utilizing online platforms.</i>) Sheila (Lines 26-30)</p> <p>“Knowing your target market... online presence... enhance customer service... new product...” (<i>It is important to know your target market, maintain a strong online presence, enhance customer service, and introduce new products.</i>) Claire (Lines 110-118)</p> <p>“Mas nisaka among sales kai katong geimprove namo among online... Mayo pud amoang response rate ug customer service.” (<i>Our sales increased because we improved our online</i></p>

		<i>presence, and our response rate and customer service also became better.”)</i> Shiela (Lines 38-42)
	3. Innovation, Creativity, and Growth	“Magintroduce nasab ka ug new para naa nasab silay bag ong anhaan sa imong store.” (“ <i>You introduce new products so that customers have fresh options to explore in your store.</i> ”) Claire (Lines 60-63)
		Ang importante na dili magundang ug pangita ug pamaage permanente ug unsaon pagimprove sa system na makatabang sa customer ug sa atoa pud.” (“ <i>The important thing is to continuously seek ways to permanently improve systems that benefit both the customers and the business.</i> ”) Sheila (Lines 89-91)
		“Continual improvement sa emong product. Plus, another strategy, continuing education sa emong staff... continuing education... invest in people.” (“ <i>We focus on continual improvement of our products. Another strategy is providing continuing education for our staff, emphasizing investment in people.</i> ”) Mark (Lines 137-147)

Theme 1. Adaptive and Ethical Strategies for Sustainability

Category 1: Adaptability, Resilience, and Sustainability

This category highlights how MSME owners sustain competitiveness by adjusting operations, demonstrating resilience during crises, supporting employees, and maintaining business continuity. Participants emphasized the importance of flexibility and strength in responding to challenges, as expressed by Sheila (Lines 11–13), “Ang pagkacompetitive sa Negosyo kai kanang kabalo ka moadjust ug molevel sa uban... magpabilin na lig-on ug kasaligan pud sa customer” (“Business competitiveness involves the ability to adapt and align with industry standards while maintaining stability and reliability for customers.”). These experiences are supported by literature identifying adaptability and resilience as key drivers of long-term competitiveness and organisational learning (Teece, 2007; Duchek, 2020; Lengnick-Hall & Beck, 2005; Zahari et al., 2023). Sustainability further reinforces competitive advantage by preserving brand identity and ethical practices (Barney, 1991; Setiawan et al., 2023).

Category 2: Ethical and Strategic Business Practices

Participants underscored the importance of maintaining ethical integrity in decision-making, even when it leads to short-term financial disadvantage. As Mark Mark (Lines

105-106) stated, “Naa may mga butang na dili, non-negotiable man gyud para sa amo. So, siges na lang. Kung magansi me din ma gansi me.” (*“There are certain things that are truly non-negotiable for us. So, we simply accept it. If we incur losses, then we incur losses.”*). This reflects research showing that ethical behaviour strengthens brand loyalty and resilience during crises (Junior et al., 2022). Strategic planning anchored in ethical values also enhances organisational performance and credibility (Abalala et al., 2021; Mousa et al., 2024).

Category 3: Financial Management and Stability

Financial discipline and preparedness emerged as vital for maintaining stability and competitiveness. Participants highlighted the importance of financial buffers to withstand disruptions, with Rolly noting the need for a “buffer” during downturns (Lines 20–22). “Ang Negosyo sa uban na prinsipyo nanginahanglan jud ni ug buffer. Kung wala ang buffer, murag paengon jud ta ana ug down.” (*“A business, based on the principles we follow, really needs a financial buffer. Without that buffer, the business is at risk of going down.”*). This aligns with studies showing that effective financial risk management and working capital discipline enhance SME stability and long-term performance (Xu, 2023; Tenedero et al., 2024).

Category 4: Values, Vision, and Brand Identity

Strong organizational values, a clear vision, and an authentic brand identity were emphasized as foundations of sustainable competitiveness. Mark’s statement (Lines 48–49), “Pangitag paagi, without losing your identity” (*“Find ways to innovate, but without losing your identity”*), reflects the importance of preserving core principles while adapting to change. This is supported by research linking mission and vision clarity to stronger competitive positioning and stakeholder trust (Contreras-Pacheco et al., 2022; Bertolini et al., 2024).

Theme 2. Customer-Centric Innovation and Digital Transformation

Category 1: Customer-Centered Excellence

Participants highlighted that prioritizing customer needs, delivering quality service, and building relationships lead to loyalty and repeat business. As Jade (Lines 17–19) explained, “Atimanon natog maayo atong customer para ang customer man gud is kung mayo ka moentertain sa ilaha magbalik balik gyud na sa imo, dili jud ka mabyaan.” (*“We take good care of our customers because if you provide excellent service, they will keep coming back, ensuring customer loyalty.”*). This approach strengthens customer satisfaction and aligns with studies showing that customer-focused quality management enhances competitive advantage (Jaya et al., 2024; Lankauskienė et al., 2025).

Category 2: Digitalization and Online Presence

Maintaining a strong digital presence was recognised as essential in today’s market.

Sheila (Lines 26-30) emphasized, “Kabalo pud me moadopt sa bag ong mga teknolohiya... gagamit me ug more on sa online.” (“*We are also capable of adopting new technologies, with a strong focus on utilising online platforms.*”). This is supported by literature indicating that digitalisation and online engagement significantly improve visibility, efficiency, and competitiveness (Umar et al., 2023; Small Business Economics, 2024).

Category 3: Innovation, Creativity, and Growth

Continuous innovation and process improvement were identified as drivers of growth and competitiveness. Sheila (Lines 89–91) stated, “Ang importante na dili magundang ug pangita ug pamaage permanente ug unsaon pagimprove sa system na makatabang sa customer ug sa atoa pud.” (“*The important thing is to continuously seek ways to permanently improve systems that benefit both the customers and the business.*”), highlighting the importance of ongoing improvement. Research confirms that sustained innovation and creative problem-solving increase growth potential and strengthen competitive advantage (Wang et al., 2025; Hanoum et al., 2025).

Conclusions

This study concludes that *digital solutions* and *eco-friendly practices* are important factors associated with the *business competitiveness* of MSMEs in Cagayan de Oro City. The results provide support for the Resource-Based View (RBV) and Porter’s Competitive Advantage Theory by indicating that the strategic use of digital tools and sustainability-oriented practices aligns with stronger market presence, operational efficiency, and financial performance.

The study underscores the relevance of integrating digitalisation and environmental responsibility as complementary strategies in enhancing MSMEs’ competitive positioning. *Digital solutions* support market access and operational processes, while *eco-friendly practices* contribute to business credibility and customer confidence.

Qualitative insights further highlight the role of adaptability, ethical business practices, and customer-oriented innovation in sustaining competitiveness. Overall, the study suggests that MSMEs that deliberately align digital strategies with sustainability initiatives are better positioned to remain competitive in a dynamic and evolving business environment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are provided to boost the competitiveness of MSMEs in Cagayan de Oro through *digital solutions* and *eco-friendly practices*.

1. Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). MSMEs are encouraged to adopt digital tools, such as Lazada, Shopee, and Facebook, to improve efficiency, reach, and

competitiveness. Integrating *eco-friendly practices* and energy-efficient technologies can enhance performance and appeal to environmentally conscious consumers. Additionally, continual improvement through staff training, continuous system enhancement, and product or service development can strengthen overall business capabilities.

2. Local Government Units (LGUs) and Policymakers. Local governments and policymakers should provide support through training programs, digital infrastructure, and incentives that encourage eco-friendly and technologically driven business practices. Expanding financial support and capacity-building programs will strengthen MSME resilience, while fostering public-private partnerships can drive modernization and collaborative growth.

3. Future Researchers. Future research may expand the scope by incorporating participant feedback, exploring innovative evidence-based models, and fostering collaboration with government agencies, industry stakeholders, and MSME organisations to support inclusive economic development in Cagayan de Oro City.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors certify that informed consent was obtained and the respondents were informed of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time. The anonymity of the respondents was sustained. Data Privacy was secured. The respondents' well-being was maintained. No conflict of interest exists in the pursuit of this study. Plagiarism was firmly avoided. Neutrality in the interpretation of the findings was ensured. The results were used purely for research.

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